

IoT-based Wastewater Management System

¹ Muna Musallam Ahmed Hardan, ² Fatima Salim Mahad Al-awaid

^{1,2} University of Technology and Applied Sciences – Salalah, Oman

¹ 46S162327@sct.edu.om, ² 46S162630@sct.edu.om

Abstract:

Wastewater is a resource that is too important to be wasted, as fresh water is becoming increasingly limited. Large city wastewater is frequently dumped directly into rivers or the ocean without undergoing treatment, causing pollution, and endangering both human and the environment. Innovations in the field of the Internet of Things, as well as its broad use around the world, have improved quality of life. By connecting sensors and microcontrollers and connecting it to the internet have allowed us to create useful projects that will benefit the community. Our project's goal is to make UTAS get benefits from the used water and reused it, to remove suspended solids and harmful toxic elements, and improve water quality to permissible level before discharging into bodies of water or for use in agricultural land. It would make it easy for the administration of our university to monitor and manage, thus improving our health and environment. We will use the Internet of Things in our project, which will use sensors to detect, compute, and monitor PH and turbidity levels in the wastewater. The water will be pumped through a holding tank to remove suspended solids then filtered and treated with chlorine. The water level is also monitored in the tank. A warning or notification is provided if the PH and turbidity values are not within acceptable limits. Furthermore, data from the sensors will be uploaded to a cloud database for later analysis and devices can be accessed through the internet using an online IoT Platform.

Keywords: Internet of Things (IoT), sensors, wastewater, treatment, environment